

2014

REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL
JOURNAL

VOL III Issues IV

**Electronic
International
Interdisciplinary
Research
Journal(EIIRJ)**

ISSN : (2277-8721)

Impact factor:0.987

Chief-Editor: Ubale Amol Baban

A STUDY OF SELF MOTIVATION

Prof. Dr. Vinay Bhole

Associate Professor

Model College, Dombivli

There are a large number of theories in management on the subject of Motivation. This management concept of human motivation requires 'someone' to motivate.

In day-to-day life what motivates us? The conventional necessities like food, clothing, shelter or most of the times....the feel of 'show must go on', that is, just one more day to go.

The workers and staff members in any organization after satisfying financial needs like wages, salaries, bonus, overtime, allowances etc. like to have something called non-financial motivation in the form of rewards, awards, recognition and acceptance from others.

Acceptance from co-workers or co-staff is the self-esteem stage. When they are unable to reach to that stage, leader or manager has to help them to achieve it.

It is like Bhagwan Shri Krishna motivated Arjun to plunge into war.

But there are some unanswerable events in human life. Human beings other than routine acts in their life do many things for which they may not be able to give exact explanation.

That is, why they do it?

The answer is they are immensely 'Self-motivated'.

In normal ideology of motivation, the motivation itself may be positive or negative. Though it is powerful at a particular point of time, it has certain time period after which it comes to an end and the individual has to be given another dose of motivation.

But self-motivation has its origin from within. It has its own birth and up gradation. No one else can nourish it or kill it. One has to generate it for himself from within.

Once it is generated then such self-motivated people become boon to the organization, society and to their family for all the time.

There are certain examples of self motivation.

Eklavya developed his skills in archery without any Guru because he was self-motivated.

Columbus decided to change the route and discovered America because he was self-motivated.

Alexander had feeling to conquer the world though he was a king by birth because to become Emperor was the inner urge which got developed out of self-motivation only.

Bhagwan Mahavir and Bhagwan Gautam Buddha left kingdom and devoted to social upliftment of the society which was also a type of self-motivation.

In modern times,

What encouraged man to reach to moon?

Why many scientists work hard for years together to find something hypothetical in their mind as it is ignited by their self-motivation.

People who walk to Pandharpur at a very old age inspite of inability to walk as these self-motivated people have an urge to meet their God.

Narmada-parikrama is the hard task for which people walk by facing a large number of hurdles.

In a simple way to think,

When we travel to any place we feel the distance but while coming back we come fast as what we feel though the distance is the same as our motivating factor is our sweet home.

While working also, salary though it's a prime and basic motive one has to make his work enjoyable.

Sweepers sweeping road do the work so systematically and in rhythm that you can notice symmetrical lines after sweeping the road.

In hotel cooks do cut onions or vegetables very fast in a particular style, as they enjoy the way they work.

Cooks preparing rumali roti throw it up in the air and without damage to it proceed further.

In local trains of Mumbai before train stops hawkers selling nuts get down without falling a single nut on platform.

Shoe polishwala do the polish with great interest.

Mumbaikar Dabbawalas apply unknowingly the logistics management.

Hawkers do calculations without calculator.

Everyone is bestowed with certain skills qualities. One has to utilize it positively.

If we take example of animals,

Why and how birds travel thousands of miles in a particular season to a particular place?

What motivates honeybees to take tremendous efforts and to collect honey?

Nature has given everyone a task to be completed with rhythm, responsibility, zeal and enthusiasm.

Maximum people if asked in the morning, 'why you saw today's morning?'

The answer may be, its routine, its next or one more day in my life. But some negative people say, 'because in sleep I did not die.'

Life is that how we take it. The same is to be applied in work culture. If one changes attitude, the whole world looks new though it is the same. If work becomes enjoyable, the person doing it never feels about it. This miracle is done by the driving force behind it that is "Self-Motivation".

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